

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' INTENTION TO CONTINUE MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSES

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Introduction

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are gradually and fast growing and more popular among educational institutions, learners, and researchers (Spector,2014). As of 2020, the top MOOC platforms were Coursera, edX, FutureLearn and Swayam (Shah, 2020). In the MOOC environment, both the number of attendees and the level of user contributions have increased recently. For example, Coursera is increasing the number of students who use MOOCs (Ting Wang, et al., 2021). Participants sign up for MOOCs for free in most circumstances and pay a low or minimal amount to receive a completion certificate in others. Even though many MOOC providers provide free certificates to students who complete MOOC courses on the platform, the certificate is not a motivator to complete the MOOC (Hew and Cheung, 2014). According to the study, following their first MOOC encounter, up to 90% of learners stop learning online. (Hew and Cheung, 2014). Therefore, various countries have researched factors influencing university students' intention to continue MOOCs (Ting Wang, et al., 2021; Hai Min Dai, et al., 2020). However, In Sri Lanka, it is rare to find studies that research the factors that may influence university students' intention to continue MOOCs. Therefore, the research problem of this study is to identify factors that influence university students' intention to continue MOOCs in Sri Lanka.

This study aims to determine factors that influence university students' intention to continue MOOCs, and to test the relationship between identified factors and university students' intention to continue MOOCs.

The finding of the analysis will be useful to future researchers who study the various aspect of online courses. The study can help education institutions reduce the risk of failure and overcome difficulties during MOOCs. Moreover, those in education institutions can use the research findings of the study as a foundation to imitate related studies related to the MOOCs.

The relevant literature on e-learning is analysed in this part from the viewpoint of the IS success model. (Also known as the DeLone and McLean IS success model was developed by DeLone and McLean (DeLone and McLean, 1992; 2002; 2003)). Then the theoretical foundations of the Technology Acceptance Model (introduced by F.D. Davis,1989) are analysed in the context of students' intention to continue Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). For the following reasons, I combined these two theoretical models. In the beginning, prior research has combined the IS Success Model and the TAM to explain why people want to reuse e-learning. (Li et al. 2012, Yang, et al, 6 2017). Users' attitudinal assumptions, such as perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, would be influenced by IS success factors.

Methodology

A conceptual model was developed based on Yang, et al (2017). This is illustrated in Figure 1. The most frequently identified factors were used as independent variables (System quality, Course quality, and Service quality) and mediating variables (Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU)) of the conceptual model considering the previous research findings. This research model describes the relationships between these constructs and consistent hypotheses (H1–H8).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

This study used a questionnaire to operationalize the conceptual framework. Questionnaire survey items took from the prior literature and rebuilt as suitable for this study (Yang, et al., 2017; Shao, 2017). Each construct-related questionnaire item is evaluated on a seven-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating strongly disagree and 7 indicating strongly agree. The quantitative method was used for this research study. This study used cross-sectional method. This study collected data from 26th February 2021 to 11th March 2021.

The population of this research study is university students who have the continuance intention of MOOCs in Sri Lanka. Sample population to represent the entire population. It covers all university students with the continuance intention of MOOCs in Sri Lanka. Due to the time constraint, few universities were selected as the sample. The study used a convenient sample from seven national universities adding up to 160 university responses. The research model was examined, and hypotheses were tested using the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique. The SmartPLS used for advanced data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis of the respondents shown Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Characteristics

Items	Types	Numbers	Percentage
Gender	Male	51	32%
	Female	109	68%
University	University of Sri Jayewardenepura	78	49%
	University of Colombo	22	14%
	University of Kelaniya	31	13%
	University of Ruhuna	21	19%
	University of Sabaragamuwa	4	2%
	University of Rajarata	3	1%
	University of Peradeniya	1	1%
Year	1 st year	0	0%
	2 nd year	23	15%
	3 rd year	42	26%
	4 th year	95	59%

The above table illustrates that 32% of the respondents are male, and 68% of the respondents are female. 0% of the respondents are 1st-year undergraduates, 15% of the respondents are 2nd-year undergraduates, 26% of the respondents are 3rd-year undergraduates, and 59% of the respondents are 4th-year undergraduates.

Smart PLS was then used to investigate the structural model. The bootstrapping approach with the re-sampling method was employed to produce valid standard errors or t-values and to analyze the statistical significance of the parameter estimations (Temme et al. 2006). All factor loadings above 0.7, and the AVE of each construct exceeded 0.5, showing that the constructs had good convergent validity. The square root of each construct's AVE exceeds the correlation of that construct with other

constructs. It indicates that the constructs have good discriminant validity. The hypotheses test results were exhibited in Table 2.

Table 2: Significance testing result of the Conceptual Model

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	t-Statistics	Result
H1	System_Quality Continuance_Intention	-> 0.141	3.469***	Accepted
H2	Course_Quality Continuance_Intention	-> -0.197	4.082***	Rejected
H3	Service_Quality Continuance_Intention	-> 0.117	6.024***	Accepted
H4	System_Quality Perceived_Ease_of_Use	-> 0.630	5.752***	Accepted
H5	Course_Quality Perceived_Usefulness	-> 0.397	2.142***	Accepted
H6	Service_Quality Perceived_Usefulness	-> 0.278	2.719***	Accepted
H7	Perceived_Ease_of_Use Continuance_Intention	-> 0.438	2.361***	Accepted
H8	Perceived_Usefulness Continuance_Intention	-> 0.443	9.667***	Accepted

Note: *** p<0.05

Conclusion

This study identified factors that influence university students' intention to continue MOOCs through the literature review. These are the System Quality, Service Quality, Course Quality, Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness. System quality, Course Quality and Service quality are the independent variables. Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness are the mediating factors.

This study identified the relationship between identified factors and university students' intention to continue MOOCs. Perceived Ease of Use, System Quality, and Service Quality positively affect the continuance

intention of MOOCs and Course Quality negatively affects the continuance intention of MOOCs. System Quality positively affects the Perceived Ease of Use of MOOCs. Course Quality and Service Quality positively affect MOOCs' Perceived Usefulness. Moreover, education institutions can use the study's research findings as a foundation to imitate related studies related to the MOOCs.

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